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ABSTRACT BOOK

Posters

Assessment of the physical characteristics of the elderly population

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Introduction: Sarcopenia is mentioned as one of the diseases associated with the aging process.

Methods: This study included respondents - pensioners over 65 years old. Data were collected on age, gender, level of education, marital status, number of household members, whether they live in an apartment or a house, the presence of certain diseases, regular use of medications, and whether the respondents are smokers. Hand grip strength was measured with a dynamometer; SPPB questionnaire.

Results: Out of a total of 70 respondents, 51 of them were female (72.86%) and 19 were male (27.14%). The average value of hand grip measurement with a dynamometer, for both genders, of the right hand is 26.69 kg (SD=10.92; SE=1.31) and the left hand is 26.32 kg (SD=10.29; SE=1.31). The average grip strength of the right hand of men is 39.68 kg (SD=7.67; SE=1.76) and that of the left hand is 40.39 kg (SD=8.71; SE=2.05). The average grip strength of the right hand of women is 22.09 kg (SD=5.81; SE=0.81) and that of the left hand is 21.08 kg (SD=6.29; SE=0.88). The average number of points achieved on the SPPB test is 6.75 (SD=1.32; SE=0.16). Males had slightly better results - 7.28 (SD=1.36; SE=0.32) compared to females - 6.57 (SD=1.27; SE=0.18).

Conclusion: The research results indicate that the results of the SPPB test of the elderly population in Novi Sad are lower compared to the values obtained in other world populations.

Keywords: SPPB questionnaire, hand grip strength, elderly population, sarcopenia